

Scaled TaN barriers for Cu interconnects: Reliability performance

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Abstract—One approach to continue the use of Cu in advanced nodes is to reduce the thickness of the barrier and liner. This reduction will allow more Cu in the trench that will reduce the global resistance of the wires and vias. We study the reliability performance of scaled PVD TaN barriers with a CVD Co or Ru liner in integrated structures. TDDB measurements show that all studied systems keep their Cu barrier properties when measured at 100°C. CCS-TVS measurements show Cu gets mobile at 200°C suggesting defects are present in our barrier/liner systems, where their impact on reliability at lower temperatures remain unclear. Regarding electromigration, we see a difference between using Co or Ru liner. While for a 3nm TaN/1nm Co system we observed voids in some vias, for scaled TaN barriers in combination with Ru liners, we only observed voids along the line suggesting the TaN/Ru barrier liner system is more scalable. An average E_A of about 0.9eV was observed for all the TaN/Ru systems, as expected for a system with SiCN cap. This results confirm that TaN/Ru is more scalable towards smaller dimensions making it a promising candidate in advanced nodes.

Keywords— PVD TaN scaling, Electromigration, controlled I-V, TDDB, CCS-TVS

I. INTRODUCTION

The continuous scaling of back-end-of-line (BEOL) Cu interconnect technology has become a serious challenge for the recent CMOS technologies. Line widths and wire cross-sectional areas will continue to decrease over time. The increase of the Cu wire and via resistance with decreasing dimensions will limit the overall circuit performance. One solution to reduce the higher Cu resistivity for smaller areas is to increase the Cu area by reducing the area occupied by the barrier and liner. Thin CVD Ru and Co liners in combination with a PVD TaN barrier have been widely studied as replacement for the PVD Ta liner due to their better Cu gap-fill performance [1][4]. However, it has been a challenge to scale down the barrier thickness. Thinner PVD TaN barriers must be continuous to ensure a void-free Cu filling and keeping at the same time its Cu barrier properties, therefore it is necessary to study their reliability performance, where scaled barrier/liner systems must meet both the TDDB and electromigration requirements at operational conditions. Previous work reported by Witt et al., [5], suggests that intrinsically, the standard PVD TaN barrier by itself cannot be scaled below 2nm to prevent Cu drift. Although, when PVD TaN is combined with a CVD Co liner, this system meets the reliability requirements for a combination of 0.8nm TaN/2.5nm Co while the combination of PVD TaN and CVD Ru could be scaled down to 0.5nm TaN/ 2.5nm Ru

In this paper we will extend previous work to integrated structures and we evaluate the TDDB and EM performance of scaled TaN barriers in combination with Ru and Co liners.

II. TEST MATERIAL

To study the performance of scaled TaN barriers in integrated structures, we use two different test vehicles. The first one is a M1/M2 Cu dual damascene with 44nm pitch where interconnects are integrated in a M1 stack with a porous low-k 2.55 (OSG-2.55) dielectric. The M1 trenches were integrated using SADP and filled with undoped Cu using a 3nm TaN/1nm Co as barrier/liner scheme and electroplating. M1 integration was finished with CMP and a SiCN cap. M2 dual damascene structures were patterned in a OSG-2.55, with self-aligned vias defined using EUV lithography and SADP for metal patterning. The second test vehicle is a M1/M2 Cu dual damascene with 36nm pitch where both metal levels and vias are patterned using EUV lithography. Interconnects are integrated in a SiO₂ dielectric in M1 and metallized with undoped Cu using a 3nm TaN/1nm Ru barrier/liner. The dielectric used on M2 is an OGS-2.55, trenches and vias are filled with undoped Cu, followed by CMP and SiCN cap. All wafers were finished with an 800nm thick passivation in which Al contacts were formed for the electrical probing. Wafers received a final 420°C-20min sintering anneal.

Barrier performance assessment was done on wafers processed on the first test vehicle while for electromigration wafers from both test vehicles were used, although the width of the tested line was fixed to allow for benchmarking. In both cases, the splits on barrier/liner systems was done on the M2 trenches as detailed on Table I and Table II, respectively. Note that the specified thicknesses correspond to the nominal values on field. Due to the non-conformal coverage from the PVD process, the actual barrier thickness on the sidewalls of the trench will be smaller (expected around 2nm for 3nm nominal).

III. BARRIER PERFORMANCE

Table I indicates the different systems tested for barrier properties. TaN barrier was scaled from 3nm down to 1.5nm in combination with a Ru liner. One of the major concerns when scaling down the barrier is to ensure its continuity along the trench, therefore, a combination of 1.5nm TaN and 1.5nm Mn-based barrier was also fabricated. The purpose of this approach is to use the self-forming barrier as a possible healer of a discontinuous TaN layer as such self-forming barrier by itself does not meet the TDDB barrier requirements [6]. Additionally, we also tested a 3nm TaN/1nm Co system as

reference, but no splits were fabricated using this liner scheme, as it was shown previously that this system is less scalable [7].

TABLE I: M2 METALLIZATION SPLITS TO STUDY BARRIER PERFORMANCE.

Splits	Barrier	Liner
#1	3nm TaN	1nm Ru
#2	2nm TaN	1nm Ru
#3	1.5nm TaN	1nm Ru
#4	1.5nm TaN + 1.5nm Mn-based	1nm Ru
#5	3nm TaN	1nm Co

To evaluate the barrier performance, controlled-I-V measurements on fork-fork structures were performed. This technique allows to establish a direct link between the time to failure (TTF) and the breakdown voltage (V_{BD}) and has been reported to give equivalent results as standard TDDB measurements [8].

Measurements at 25°C allow us to check the sanity of the structures, as no metal drift is expected at such low temperatures. It can be seen in Figure 1 that the calculated acceleration factors for all tested wafers are ~20, which correspond to expected acceleration factor for a porous low-k dielectric [11].

Figure 1: Calculated acceleration factor for all tested splits measured at 25°C and 100°C.

Measurements at 100°C on similar devices also show high acceleration factors ($m \sim 20$) for all splits suggesting good barrier performance. In Figure 2, we show the failure time $t_{63.2\%}$ vs. electric field, fitted by using the power law model ($t_{63.2\%} \sim V^{-m}$).

Figure 2: Lifetime extrapolation using power law model for all tested systems at 100°C.

To further assess the barrier properties, triangular voltage sweep (TVS) measurements combined with constant current stress (CCS) were performed at 200°C **Error! Reference source not found.** Results obtained on the 3nm TaN/1nm Ru system are shown on Figure 3. The non-stable high current seen on the first TVS sweep performed after CCS, indicates Cu drifting into de dielectric [9]. Similar output was obtained for all the other splits, suggesting defects are present in our barrier/liner systems, where their impact on reliability at lower temperatures remain unclear. As TVS measurements do not give information about

failure times, and it is essential to evaluate whether these barriers meet lifetime specifications at operating conditions, it will be necessary to collect packaged TDDB data at high temperatures during longer times. In, Chen et al. [9], it is proposed to test more than 300 hours at 200°C to ensure that there will be no metal drift happening at 100°C within 10 years.

Figure 3: 1st and 2nd TVS results on a 3nm TaN/1nm Ru barrier system which was subjected to CCS at 200°C.

IV. ELECTROMIGRATION

The second reliability aspect that is investigated is Electromigration (EM). Via failures during electromigration, were investigated by testing dual damascene (DD) lines with wide (>80nm) M1 feeder line, a 22nm wide via and a 23nm wide, >100µm long M2 line. This design ensures that voids only form in the upper metal layer. Upstream electromigration was performed on samples detailed in Table II by applying a current density of 1.68MA/cm² through the via. Packaged samples were placed in the oven and resistance was measured at temperatures ranging from 200°C to 330°C. Electromigration failure times were determined by using a failure criterion of 20% resistance change.

TABLE II: M2 METALLIZATION SPLITS USED FOR EM.

Splits	Barrier	Liner	Via	Patterning
#1	3nm TaN	1nm Co	Cu	SADP
#2	3nm TaN	1nm Ru	Cu	SADP
#3	2nm TaN	1nm Ru	Cu	EUV
#4	1.5nm TaN + 1nm Mn-based	1nm Ru	Cu	SADP
#5	1.5nm TaN + 1nm Mn-based	1nm Ru	ELD Co	SADP

TEM/EDS analysis confirmed the good fill was achieved for all metallization options. We illustrate this statement in Figure 4 where a cartoon and a cross-section TEM/EDS of a structure from split #4 is shown.

Figure 4: Cartoon and cross-section TEM/EDS for split #4 showing the good filling performance of this metallization.

The lognormal probability plot of the failure times together with the fit of the Arrhenius model for 3nm TaN/1nm Co is shown in Figure 5. The tested samples show a bimodal behavior of the failure times. Through TEM and top-down SEM, we correlated the early failures with voids inside the via and the late failures with voids in the top M2 line. The occurrence of early fails could be explained by preexisting micro voids in the Cu via or poor via fill [10].

Figure 5: Samples from 3nm TaN/1nm Co show a bimodal behavior with early and late failures that was correlated to via and line voiding respectively.

Similarly, Figure 6 shows the MTTF distribution for the TaN/Ru splits where it can be seen the failure times follow a monomodal distribution with similar sigma for all temperature conditions for all splits suggesting the same failure mechanism for the three different barriers, independently on the patterning approach.

Figure 6: MTTF for 3 temperatures and $j=1.68\text{MA}/\text{cm}^2$ through the via for (a) 3nm TaN/1nm Ru; (b) 2nm TaN/1nm Ru and (c) 1.5nm TaN/1nm Mn-based/1nm Ru.

Through top-down SEM inspections we could observe that failures occurred along the M2 line and no via failures were observed, confirming the good via filling metallization that is possible with a CVD Ru liner. Two examples for the extreme cases (split #2 and split #4) are shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Top-down SEM inspection of lines after EM stress show failures along the line for (a) 3nm TaN/1nm Ru and (b) 1.5nm TaN/1.5nm Mn-based/1nm Ru.

Table III summarizes the results of the fits of the reliability parameters. Similar activation energies ($E_A=0.9\text{eV}$) and similar sigma ($\sigma=0.50$) were obtained for all systems with voiding along the M2 line. These are expected results for undoped Cu lines with a SiCN cap. Nevertheless, it can be seen that for the same stress conditions, the samples experience shorter failure times with decreasing TaN barrier thickness. A possible explanation for this could be related to a decrease in confinement of the copper in the trench.

TABLE III: ESTIMATES OF RELIABILITY PARAMETERS.

Barrier/Liner		$t_{50\%}(h)$ 280°C-1.68MA/cm ²	E_A (eV)	σ
3nm TaN /1nm Co	Via failures	5.9 (4.1 – 8.5)	0.91±0.2	0.6 (0.4 – 1.0)
	Line failures	34.4 (30.5 – 38.9)	0.85±0.07	0.2 (0.1 – 0.3)
3nm TaN/ 1nm Ru		14.3 (9.2 – 22.3)	0.96±0.1	0.5 (0.4 – 0.9)
2nm TaN/ 1nm Ru		6.7 (4 – 11.1)	0.91±0.15	0.6 (0.5 – 0.8)
1.5nm TaN + 1nm Mn-based/1nm Ru		5.3 (4.2 – 6.7)	0.91±0.07	0.4 (0.3 – 0.5)
1.5nm TaN + 1nm Mn-based/1nm Ru + Co via		5.4 (3.6 – 8.1)	1.03±0.12	0.6 (0.5, 0.9)

In Figure 8 we show the lognormal distributions of the failure times for split #5 where we combine the self-forming barrier route in M2 lines with ELD Co vias. The reliability parameters for this approach, (Table III), show similar results to split #4 with Cu vias and top-down SEM inspection shows also, voiding along the M2 line confirming the robustness of the ELD Co vias. Provided that issues with adhesion and metal intermixing are resolved [7], hybrid approaches using Co vias could become a solution to further using Cu on reduced dimensions.

Figure 8: (a) MTTF for 3 temperatures and $j=1.68\text{MA}/\text{cm}^2$ through the via for split #5 (b) Top down SEM image showing voiding along the M2 line.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work summarizes the reliability study done on thin PVD TaN barriers in combination with CVD Co and Ru liners. Controlled IV measurements done at 100°C indicate good barrier performance for TaN barriers scaled down to 1.5nm, in combination with 1nm Ru or Co liner. However, TVS measurements at 200°C suggest Cu drifts at these temperatures, where its impact on reliability would need to be assessed by long-term measurements at high temperatures. Electromigration results show that scaled TaN barrier in combination with CVD Co suffers from via failures, stating therefore its limitation for further scaling. For all studied TaN/Ru systems, electromigration results show voiding along the line and similar activation energies to Cu lines capped with SiCN. These results confirm the promising capability of TaN/Ru systems for further scaling.

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